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**ASSESSMENT OF TEACHING APPROACHES FOR INSTRUCTIONAL IMPROVEMENT IN
SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ABAKILIKI EDUCATIONAL ZONE, EBONYI STATE**

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ABSTRACT

This research centered on the assessment of teaching approaches for instructional improvement in secondary schools in Abakiliki educational zone, Ebonyi state. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey research design with random sampling techniques was used. The population of the study was made up of all the 3220 teachers of the public secondary schools in the Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state. A sample size of 356 respondents was used, using Taro-Yamane's formula to draw from the population across the education zone. Instrument for data collection was a researcher-made questionnaire duly validated and the reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha, which yielded a co-efficient index of 0.82. The researcher and 5 research assistants administered and retrieved the questionnaire; with 97.3% return rate. Mean and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The analyzed data revealed among others that the teachers mostly employed teaching strategies like the experimental and the independent teaching strategies for instructional delivery improvement in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state. The study recommended among others that the Government should support the secondary schools through adequate funding in order to avail teachers with opportunities to employ teaching strategies as workshops, field observation, simulation and games, industrial cooperative methods and many other demonstrative methods.

Keywords: Instructional Delivery, Improvement, Teaching Approaches, Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Education serves as a comprehensive instrument for societal empowerment and socioeconomic advancement. Thus, teacher effectiveness, efficiency, productivity, and quality continue to be the best indicators of student achievement. Given all of the available information, a teacher must create effective teaching strategies to aid students in learning in the classroom. Teachers' usage of these strategies during classroom interactions determines how well students learn and understand the materials. Instead of just accepting that certain students are incapable of being involved and are destined to fail, effective teachers make an effort to engage and excite all of their students in the learning process (OECD, 2016). By saying in the National Policy on Education (NPE) that "every Nigerian child should have access to quality education relevant to the needs of the Nigerian Economy, the FRN (2013) further highlighted the significance of effective teaching practices, which included that all instruction must be immersive, activity-based, learner-centered, practical, and IT-supported. In a similar vein, Adebayo

in Ogwunte and Okolocha (2016) pointed out that effective and significant teaching and learning requires more than just teachers having the necessary training and expertise in their fields. There is also the need for emphasis to be placed on effective planning with competent teachers to ensure mastery and proper use of relevant strategies for teaching knowledge, competencies and skills in the work place for technical and socio- economic development.

In essence, high quality teachers that utilize effective teaching strategies or methodologies are the most important factor in any students' education and learning. Teaching strategies are several approaches to making judgments regarding a course, a single class, or even an entire curriculum, all of which begin with an examination of essential aspects in the teaching environment. Effective planning with qualified teachers is also necessary to guarantee mastery and appropriate use of pertinent techniques for imparting knowledge, skills and competencies in the workplace for technical and socioeconomic development. The most crucial element in each student's education and learning is, in essence, excellent teachers who apply efficient teaching techniques. A subject, a single class, or even a whole curriculum can be evaluated using a variety of methods known as teaching techniques and all of which start with an analysis of the key elements of the classroom. According to Shinn (2009), teaching strategies are the complex ways in which a teacher uses which can be in form of discipline, tools, tactics, procedures, and communications to accomplish educational goals and/or objectives. Teaching strategies, according to Oden (2015), include everything a teacher does to facilitate learning, including setting up environments, assigning students to groups, supervising activities, and producing assignments. Akpan and Oden (2015) defined teaching strategies as the practice and improvement of presentation that a teacher uses to make his instruction more (effective) and enjoyable while using a certain method or teaching equipment. Therefore, teaching strategies are methods, procedures, styles, tactics, or ways that a business school teacher has chosen to help the teaching-learning process, as described in the context of the current study. Students learn and develop their competencies when teachers use effective teaching tactics. Some of the teaching strategies used in business education have been identified by various scholars (Adediran, Orukotan & Adeyanju, 2015). These include demonstration, discussion, role-play/socio drama, lecture, questioning, discovery/inquiry-based learning, explanations, brain storming, practice or practical exercises, field trip, excursion, narration, modelling, guest speaker, direct instruction, rote learning, query method, activity method, debate, conferencing, cooperative learning, graphic organising, and more. Operationally, the teaching methods under context are experimental and interactive teaching strategies. Experimental teaching strategies involve engaging students in hands-on activities and experiments to deepen their understanding of a subject. This approach emphasizes active learning, problem-solving, and critical thinking, moving beyond traditional lecture-based methods. It is a method that has been described as problem solving, critical thinking, deductive thinking and not mere personal assumptions. It is a method of teaching that involves probing, finding out, investigating, analyzing, synthesizing, discovering, evaluating, questioning and thinking. According to Senthamarai (2018), interactive teaching is one that engages learners in the process of learning rather than delivering ready-made materials for learners' consumption. In that sense, the teacher and the learner have to take active roles in the process of teaching and learning. The author particularly argues that interactive teaching approach is a new approach that fosters interaction among learners as teachers lead the process of learning. In this type of approach, "the teacher must use particular methods to encourage discovery learning. The interactive teaching approach helps learners to become more engaged in learning and retain more information

According to Canuel (2008), good teaching practices help students think more clearly by helping them understand concepts that will help them solve problems, encouraging them to collaborate with others using ICT, for example, to solve problems, helping them explain how they think about complex problems, encouraging students in micro units to come up

with a coordinated solution to tasks or challenges, and helping them stay active. Effective teaching tactics, according to Ukata, Wechie, and Nmehielle (2017), assist students with guided and autonomous practice, modelling, and dealing with real-life situations. They provide a forum for students to demonstrate their knowledge, thoughts, and existing language on a specific topic; only then does it make sense for the children's education. A good teaching strategy doesn't try to cover too much or too little in a given class. For the entire lesson, the teacher's planned material should be adequate. The substance of a lesson should be determined by the learners' age, interest, aptitude, and maturity as well as the type of material to be taught. According to Ukata, Wechie, and Nmehielle (2017), effective teaching strategies help students practice both independently and under guidance, model behaviour, and handle real-world scenarios. According to the aforementioned, teaching strategies that incorporate approaches, procedures, means, actions, or methods for accomplishing the stated educational goals are seen to be essential for students' learning and academic success; they play an important and noticeable part in the teaching and learning process. At the secondary school level, effective teaching and learning methods are crucial for the education / learning. However, a look at modern Nigerian culture, and Ebonyi State in particular, shows that in order for any young person to be useful in their career, they must acquire technical know-how and practical abilities. A young person without employable skills has no future; likewise education programme is useless if it fails to sufficiently address how students will learn, use technical and other useful skills.

On the basis of this premise, a great deal of research has been done on teaching methods; some have found that teaching strategies are effective in education, while others have found a combination. For instance, experts referenced in Ogwunte and Okolocha (2016) agreed that teachers, school and educational authorities, and the government were not giving effective teaching practices the proper attention. Furthermore, teaching and learning of skills in schools will continue to face obstacles, and unemployment among school dropouts with related social ills will continue to rise if prompt action is not taken to ensure effective teaching of skills at the secondary school level. In both internal and external senior secondary school certificate exams (SSCE), post-primary school students' academic performance has recently decreased as a result of teachers' failure to use effective teaching strategies (Okolocha & Ogwunte, 2016). Observations in Ebonyi State also indicate that students' poor academic performance and accomplishments have increased as a result of teachers' incapacity to use appropriate teaching tactics. It is widely accepted that if students receive the right instruction and the necessary teaching techniques, their abilities will improve and they will become high achievers who will achieve their educational objectives and realize their aspirations. Effective teaching techniques must not be taken for granted in order for this to be accomplished in education. Therefore, the goal of this study is to shed light on the instructional techniques teachers use to improve student outcomes. In light of this, the current study aimed to identify the instructional tactics used by teachers in secondary schools in the Abakiliki Educational Zone of Ebonyi State in order to enhance students' learning.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Teachers everywhere are dedicated to using effective teaching techniques to help students reach their full potential. Student academic performance is declining, according to observations made of recent events taking place in Ebonyi State's secondary schools. Many students' reading and study habits have substantially decreased or been pared down to the bare minimum, which often has an impact on their academic achievements. The most recent WASSCE and JAMB 2024 results has attested to the low academic achievement of students across a range of subjects. While there were more students with ordinary passes and those who failed certain topics, there were less students with credit and merit passes. So, one tries to find out what the issue is.

However, the majority of teachers' incapacity to improve students' learning through effective teaching practices is concerning and has drawn attention from the public, secondary school education stakeholders, and researchers. Closing this gap need an urgent response so that high-quality instruction can succeed in the State's secondary schools. Therefore, the study's challenge is to identify instructional strategies that could be used to enhance secondary school students' learning in Abakiliki Educational Zone of Ebonyi State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to determine teaching approaches that could be employed in improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

Specifically, the study intends to:

1. find out experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state
2. examine the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state?
2. What are the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses will guide the studying and will be tested at 0.5 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no statistical significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

H₀₂: There is no statistical significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Review framework

This study was informed by the constructivism learning theory. According to Phuong (2018), constructivism theory holds that "each learner creates their relative reality or at least understands it based on their knowledge and experience. He argued that constructivism is both learner centered and process oriented teaching whereby learners are guided to actively participate and construct the knowledge through the influence of the teacher. The theory recognizes the central role of the learner in all parts of the process of constructing, reconstructing and enacting knowledge.

A number of studies such as Ngussa and Makewa (2014); Ngussa and Chiza (2017) and Ngussa and Lyimo (2019) proved that constructivism approach leads to maximized learning outcomes. The studies indicated that when constructivism approach is used in the teaching and learning process, learners become active and the learning effectiveness is enhanced. According to Anh (2019), constructivism theory helps teachers to identify experiences and knowledge of learners, facilitate student-centered teaching activities, support learners in gaining new knowledge and helps them learn more effectively through hands on activities.

Eze et al. (2019) conducted a study on relative effectiveness of constructivism and meta-learning teaching methods on students' academic achievement and retention in basic electricity in technical colleges. The study revealed that constructivism teaching method improved technical college students' achievement in basic electricity. Since constructivism approach involves opportunities for learners to do while the teacher plays the role of guiding, the approach closely relates with interactive approach and yields positive results in terms of fostering students' activeness in the teaching and learning process.

A study by Ngussa and Makewa (2014) on constructivism experiences in teaching-learning transaction in selected Tanzanian secondary schools established that teachers employed constructivism principles and student academic performance was influenced by teaching modalities, active participation and classroom setup. Furthermore, high performing learners in the study tended to engage in active participation more frequently than their lower performing counterparts. Based on the findings, the study recommended that "classroom sessions should be dominated by activities that lead learners to actively seek solutions to existing problems and discover new information through a varied range of guided activities. This suggests that the knowledge construction by learners has to be done under the guidance of teachers, thus, learners should not be left alone to do as they wish without proper direction. Therefore, both the teacher and the learners need to be active in the process of teaching and learning whereby the teacher plays the role of proper guidance. Since reviewed literature did not establish studies on pupils' learning activeness in relation to teaching approach, this study sought to establish the effect of interactive teaching on pupils' activeness in learning among primary schools.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design and it was considered suitable because the opinion of a representative sample of respondents was sought using questionnaire and the finding was generalized on the entire population. The population of the study was made up of all the 3220 teachers of the public secondary schools in the Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state. A sample size of 356 respondents was used, using Taro-Yamane formular to draw from the population across the education zone. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled: Teaching Approaches for Improving Students' Learning in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (TAISLSSQ). The questionnaire was developed from literature by the researchers and used for data collection. The instrument was a four point response scale of strongly agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly disagreed (SD) with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was face – validated by three experts: Two from Department of Science Education - Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu-Alike Ikwo, Ebonyi State and one from Measurement and Evaluation Department - Ebonyi State University. Their corrections and suggestions were utilized to improve the initial copies of the questionnaire to produce the final copies. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was adopted to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire items. A Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.82 was obtained and the collected data was analyzed using mean for research questions and t-test was used for the test of hypothesis. Any mean response of 2.50 and above was considered agreed while any mean response below 2.50 was considered

disagreed. For hypothesis testing, t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis for any item was rejected when the calculated *p*-value is less than the alpha value of 0.05 but is accepted when the *p*-value is greater than the alpha value of 0.05.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state?

Data for answering research question 1 are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state (n=356)

S/N	Item statement	\bar{x}	SD	Rmk
1.	Field trips/excursion strategy allows students to have first-hand information about a subject matter	3.31	.78	Agreed
2.	Workshops enhances students engagement and understanding of complex concepts	3.40	.64	Agreed
3.	Project-based learning helps students develop critical thinking and problem solving skills.	3.39	.62	Agreed
4.	Use of simulation and games are used to promote students' learning in school	3.31	.73	Agreed
5.	Allowing students to visit offices and firms in order to expose them to the reality of what has been previously taught in the classroom enhances learning engagement	3.26	.68	Agreed
6.	Drill-and-practice method in the teaching of education subjects enhances learning engagement	3.24	.76	Agreed
7.	Laboratory exposure/demonstration method improves students practical experiments and skills to face future challenges	3.22	.75	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 1 revealed that all the 7 items had their mean ratings ranging from 3.22 to 3.40 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed on the identified experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state. The standard deviation of all the 7 items ranged from .62 to .78, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in in secondary schools.

Research Question 2

What are the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state?

Data for answering research question 2 are presented in Table 2

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state (n=356)

S/N	Item statements	\bar{x}	SD	Rmk
1.	Using interactive whiteboards in class enhances students engagements and understanding	3.22	.75	Agreed
2.	Debates helps students develop critical thinking skills in schools	2.81	1.12	Agreed
3.	Role –playing helps students develop empathy and understanding of complex issues	3.22	.75	Agreed
4.	Gamification makes learning more enjoyable and interactive	2.81	1.12	Agreed
5.	Discussion method is most commonly used for promoting students learning	3.28	.70	Agreed
6.	Interactive multi-media presentations enhances students’ understanding and retention of materials	3.22	.75	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 2 revealed that all the 6 items had their mean ratings ranging from 2.81 to 3.28 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed on all the identified interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state. The standard deviation of all the 6 items ranged from .68 to 1.12, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no statistical significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

Table 3: t-test analysis of mean difference between male and female teachers on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

Gender	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	α	Sig.	Decision
Male	223	3.39	.56	354	3.385	0.05	.001	Rejected H ₀₁
Female	133	3.20	.42					

Source: t-test Result from SPSS

Result in table 3 revealed that the p-value of 0.001 is lesser than 0.05 level of significance. Which means there is a significant difference between the mean responses of male and female teachers on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

H₀₂: There is no statistical significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

Table 4: t-test analysis of mean difference between male and female teachers on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

Gender	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	α	Sig.	Decision
Male	223	2.89	.61	354	3.00	0.05	.003	Rejected H ₀₂
Female	133	2.70	.52					

Source: t-test Result from SPSS

Data on table 4 shows that the *p*-value of 0.003 is lesser than 0.05 level of significance. Which means there is a significant difference between the mean responses of male and female teachers on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

Discussion of Findings

The findings were discussed based on the following sub-heading derived from the study objectives and research questions: experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in in secondary schools and interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state.

The responses of teachers on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in in secondary schools, the result revealed that all the 7 items had their mean ratings ranging from 3.22 to 3.40 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed on the identified experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state. The standard deviation of all the 7 items ranged from .62 to .78, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in in secondary schools. However, the findings of the above study were in agreement with the view of Umameiye (2015) who revealed that experimentation such as field trips/excursion strategy, use of simulation and flipped classrooms among others encourages students to think critically and solve problems through independent exploration; hence the process of designing an experiment, formulating hypotheses, and analyzing results enhances the ability to think logically and critically. Also, the result matched the findings of Bimbola (2010), who stated that the experimental teaching strategies facilitate the acquisition of the 21st century skills, not only for sustainable and responsibly citizenship, but also for a career in an increasing science and technology driven world society, through probing, finding out, investigating, analyzing, synthesizing, discovering, evaluating, questioning and thinking. More so, the views and observations of the authors cited on the experimental teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in in secondary schools has helped to justify the findings of the study on research question 1.

The opinion of teachers on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students’ learning in secondary schools, this indicated that the revealed that all the 6 items had their mean ratings ranging

from 2.81 to 3.28 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed on all the identified interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state. The standard deviation of all the 6 items ranged from .68 to 1.12, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state. This finding is also in line with Ihebom, & Uko (2020) who opined that interactive teaching strategies, such as group discussion, role-playing, debate, problem-solving activities, and technology-based learning, have been advocated as good ways to improve students' academic performance. They further stated interactive pedagogy can lead to enhanced academic achievement, motivation, and student satisfaction. More so, the results matches the findings of Kennewell (2015) who maintained that high quality interaction between the teacher and learners is an important element for effective teaching and learning to be realized. The researcher revealed that in interactive learning, the teacher and the learner come together as partners in the process of teaching and learning. According to the author, such classroom settings motivate a whole class of learners to actively participate in the learning process. The views and observations of the authors cited on the interactive teaching strategies that could be employed by teachers for improving students' learning in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state helped to validate the findings of the study in Table 2.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study confirm that students' academic performance is much improved by experimental and interactive teaching strategies. Nonetheless, the study demonstrates that these approaches promote greater understanding, critical thinking, and involvement. The study also emphasizes how these approaches encourage involvement and inclusivity for all secondary school students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. To improve student engagement and academic success, educators should give priority to interactive teaching strategies such group discussions, collaborative learning, and technology-enhanced instruction.
2. To provide secondary school teachers the tools they need to teach effectively, schools should offer professional development programmes
3. To encourage inclusivity and fair learning results for all groups, policymakers ought to incorporate student-centered approaches into curricula.
4. To improve secondary school students' learning, secondary school principals should support and encourage teachers to use additional direct teaching strategies like seminars, individualized instruction, peer tutoring, team teaching, and assigning students to different reading groups.
5. Government should routinely produce resources and training programs to support teachers in curriculum programmes implementation.

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